

MEDICAL SCIENCES

IMPRESSION TRAY MODIFICATION FOR FULLY EDENTULOUS

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Abstract

In specialized dental care for the population, great importance is attached to the prosthetics of patients with a complete absence of teeth. The determining factor in obtaining high-quality dentures in the complete absence of teeth is the accuracy of functional impressions. Without achieving reliable fixation of a functional impression, further efforts to manufacture complete removable dentures become problematic. The questions of methods and techniques for obtaining a functional impression are still debatable. In the specialized literature, there are no parallels between the method of obtaining a functional impression and the strength of the base of the finished prosthesis. In our opinion, this part of the study could significantly complement the task of improving the creation of highly functional prostheses for edentulous jaws

Keywords: complete absence of teeth, techniques for obtaining a functional impression, innovative impression materials.

It has been established that both men and women need orthopedic treatment with the same frequency, and the need for this type of dental care increases with age. The need for prosthetics in ranges from 35.6 to 50.64%. It has been determined that the average shelf life of removable dentures is 2–3 years [5, 10]. One of the fundamental factors for improving the quality of life and dental health of edentulous patients is reliable fixation and stabilization of removable dentures, the achievement of which is often associated with significant difficulties in obtaining functional impressions, especially for beginners [1]. At present, it should be recognized that the main method of fixing complete dentures is a method based on the use of physical laws and anatomical features of the structure of the boundaries of the prosthetic bed. This method is called biophysical. For its implementation, it is necessary to create a rarefied space on the largest possible area. This becomes possible if the suction chamber is not a limited area, but the entire basis of the prosthesis. In this case, the closing valve is formed by the edge of the prosthesis and the mucous membrane of the neutral zone, a section of the mucous membrane with significant compliance and minimal mobility [7]. Orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with complete loss of teeth is always associated with a change or restoration of the interalveolar distance, the optimal value of which has a significant impact on the functioning of the organs of the dental system. Reliable stabilization of the prostheses ensures the correct fixation of the interalveolar distance and is the key to the normal state of the organs of the maxillofacial region [3,6]. To achieve fixation, it is necessary to

obtain a clear display of the relief of the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed, taking into account the functional state of the soft tissues of the prosthetic field in the manufacture of an individual impression tray. For this purpose, in our opinion, the most suitable are polyester impression masses of the Impregum 3M ESPE line. The materials have well-pronounced mucostatic properties, which is necessary when taking impressions for removable structures, when displacement or extrusion of the mucous membrane is undesirable, as well as high hydrophilicity, thixotropy and plasticity. Monophasic and one-stage imprint eliminates the possibility of deformation due to the difference in the coefficients of elasticity of different layers, and also greatly facilitates the work of the doctor and saves time. The method of fitting an individual spoon on the edentulous lower jaw and obtaining a functional impression according to F. Herbst, who proposed to set the optimal boundaries of the spoon according to its displacement during functional tests, is widely used among orthopedic dentists. However, this method is ineffective in case of large atrophy of the alveolar process, since the functional tests proposed by Gerbst are standardized, do not take into account the individual characteristics of the patient's oral cavity and do not provide for the design of the outer polished surface of the prosthesis base in accordance with the contours of the movable anatomical structures adjacent to it. To fill this gap in the method of obtaining a functional impression from the edentulous lower jaw, P. Tanrykuliev proposed volumetric modeling of the outer polished surface of the basis of a complete removable denture of the lower jaw. Later,

many techniques were proposed for the design of the edges of an individual tray and obtaining a functional impression. Thus, some authors suggest using a material for relining complete dentures to decorate the edges of an individual tray before obtaining a functional impression, which, in our opinion, can have a negative effect on the tissues of the prosthetic field [2]. Other authors suggest using a hand-kneaded silicone edging mass to shape the edges of individual trays, while adhesive pads are placed on the inner surface of the individual trays to create a space between the individual tray and the mucosa. Subsequently, the pads are removed and a functional impression is obtained with a medium-fluid, and then with a high-fluid silicone impression mass [8]. Still others suggest edging a rigid individual tray with heated wax and obtaining a functional impression with alginate group impression materials using functional samples [9]. In addition, there is a technique for obtaining a functional impression with a rigid individual tray using stop stops made of composite material to position the tray during edging of the edges with thermoplastic mass. The subsequent functional impression is obtained using the Impregum 3M ESPE polyester material [4]. The above methods have a number of undoubted advantages, however, in our opinion, they are largely labor-intensive. The appearance on the dental market of innovative impression materials with improved properties and devices for taking an impression creates the conditions for a faster process of forming the edges of an individual tray and obtaining a functional impression during orthopedic rehabilitation of patients with complete absence of teeth. We have accumulated many years of experience in the use of the Express XT Penta Putty impression mass for the functional design of a peripheral closing valve in the neutral zone due to its excellent mucostatic properties, which eliminates horizontal displacement of the mucous membrane and allows the use of high mucosal compliance in the neutral zone to form a closing valve. 3M's new ESPE "Express XT Penta H" A-silicone material, featuring even lower viscosity and longer working time, makes it possible to form the ideal closing valve for a complete denture. According to the proposed method, an individual spoon pre-fitted with Herbst samples is shortened along the borders by 3–4 mm and the edge thickness is reduced to 1–2 mm. Thanks to the Pentamix automated mixing system, high-quality and uniform preparation of the impression mass is carried out, as well as fast and uniform application to the borders of the impression tray. In this case, it is necessary to preliminarily apply an adhesive to the surface of an individual impression tray. After placing the spoon on the prosthetic bed, it is pressed against the mucous membrane and its edges are passively formed until the impression mass is structured, while functional tests are added to form the lingual edge, which makes it possible, under difficult clinical conditions, for prosthetics on the edentulous lower jaw to always achieve adequate boundaries of the basis prosthesis and optimal design of its outer surface. After structuring, the layer of the impression mass on the outer surface of the individual tray follows the contours of the movable anatomical structures adjacent to it, and the inner layer acts

as a limiter-stopper for further positioning and creating a space between the individual tray and the mucous membrane of the prosthetic bed. To obtain a clarifying functional impression, we use a corrective material, which has excellent fluidity and is distributed over the surface in a thin layer. The mass is produced in cartridges designed for convenient dosing and mixing with a dispenser gun, which facilitates and speeds up its application to the impression tray. The applied corrective mass flows well under pressure, filling the thinnest cavities when obtaining a corrective impression, while, due to good mucostatic properties, the need to perforate the impression tray to obtain decompression is eliminated.

Findings

As a result of the application of the proposed technique in the area of the neutral zone, compression of the mucous membrane occurs, thus a differential distribution of pressure occurs due to compliance. At the same time, the property of maximum mucosal compliance in this zone is realized, which favorably affects the fixation of a removable denture. Thanks to the use of the presented technique, it is possible to quickly and accurately shape the edge of an individual spoon through the use of innovative materials and partial automation of the process.

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ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ И КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ГРАВИТАЦИОННОЙ ХИРУРГИИ В ЛЕЧЕНИИ НЕСПЕЦИФИЧЕСКОГО ЯЗВЕННОГО КОЛИТА

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RATIONALE FOR THE USE AND CLINICAL EFFICACY OF GRAVITATIONAL SURGERY IN THE TREATMENT OF NON-SPECIFIC ULCERATIVE COLITIS

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Аннотация

В статье приведены клинико-лабораторные и инструментальные данные по применению плазмафереза в лечении стероид-зависимых и стероид-резистентных форм неспецифического язвенного колита. Гормональная зависимость и резистентность – наиболее серьезная проблема в лечении НЯК. Существуют веские предпосылки для лечения стероид-резистентных и стероид-зависимых форм НЯК методом плазмафереза. Плазмаферез с непрямой электрохимической детоксикации плазмы крови с дополнительным озонированием способен качественно корригировать иммунологические нарушения, явления хронического воспаления и эндотоксикоза при НЯК.

Abstract

The article presents clinical, laboratory and instrumental data on the use of plasmapheresis in the treatment of steroid-dependent and steroid-resistant forms of ulcerative colitis. Hormonal dependence and resistance is the most serious problem in the treatment of UC. There are strong prerequisites for the treatment of steroid-resistant and steroid-dependent forms of UC by plasmapheresis. Plasmapheresis with indirect electrochemical detoxification of blood plasma with additional ozonation is able to qualitatively correct immunological disorders, chronic inflammation and endotoxemia in UC.

Ключевые слова: неспецифический язвенный колит, гормональная резистентность, гормональная зависимость, плазмаферез.

Keywords: ulcerative colitis, hormonal resistance, hormonal dependence, plasmapheresis.

Актуальность проблемы. По данным эпидемиологических исследований в настоящее время наблюдается увеличение заболеваемости неспецифическим язвенным колитом (НЯК) во всем мире. По тяжести течения, частоте осложнений и летальности НЯК занимает одно из ведущих мест в структуре болезней желудочно-кишечного тракта (Г.А. Григорьева, Н.Ю. Мешалкина, 2017; И.Л. Халиф, И.Д. Лоранская, 2019).

Хроническое рецидивирующее течение НЯК, развитие осложнений, опасных для жизни, преимущественное поражение лиц трудоспособного возраста, недостаточно эффективное, и нередко дорогостоящее его лечение, определяют актуальность

данной проблемы (Е.А. Белоусова, 2019; Ф.И. Комаров и соавт., 2018).

Цель исследования. Улучшение результатов лечения стероид-зависимых и стероид-резистентных форм неспецифического язвенного колита.

Материалы и методы исследования. Основную группу составили 47 больных, контрольную - 58 пациентов.

Основная и контрольная группы больных достоверно не отличались по полу, возрасту, соотношению гормонорезистентных и/или гормонозависимых форм НЯК, срокам формирования гормонозависимости и/или гормонорезистентности (табл. 1).